

**VUNOKLANG MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL
OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION**
(Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola)
ISSN: 2276-8114

Available online at <https://vmjste.com.ng>

INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON OFFICE TECHNOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT STUDENTS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS LEARNING IN FEDERAL POLYTECHNICS IN NORTH-EAST, NIGERIA

Nuradeen Yakubu Mohammed¹, Abdulmutallib Umar Baraya², & Umar Aliyu Abubakar³

¹ & ² Department of Vocational and Technology Education, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Nigeria

³ Department of Library and Information Science, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Nigeria

Corresponding Author: alsheikh4all@gmail.com, +23408064098528

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10359632>

Abstract

The study determined the Influence of social media on Office Technology and Management (OTM) students' attitude towards learning in Federal Polytechnics in North-east Nigeria. The study had two specific objectives, research questions and null hypotheses. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, the population of the study was 981 OTM students, the sample size for this study was two hundred and sixty-nine (269) students using proportionate random sampling techniques. Structured questionnaires were used. Data collected was analysed using mean and standard deviations while simple linear regression was used to test the null hypotheses, any item with a mean value of 2.50 and above was considered agreed while any hypothesis with a P-Value of less than 0.05 was rejected. The findings of the study revealed that effective utilization of Facebook and YouTube platforms have positive influence on students' attitude toward learning. This study therefore, recommend that Government through School Management and Lecturers should give more emphasis on the importance of communication skills together with practical skills in the use of Facebook and YouTube to students in order to meet up with the employability skills standard in the knowledge-based economy.

Keywords: Attitude, Influence, Learning, Office Technology and Management, Social Media

Introduction

Social media has exploded as a category of online discourse where people create content, share it, bookmark it and network at a prodigious rate. Because of its ease of use, speed and reach, social media is fast changing the public discourse in society and setting trends and agenda in topics that range from the environment and politics to technology and the entertainment industry (Verdegem, 2019). Social media are open, web-based, and user-friendly applications that provide new possibilities when it comes to the co-creation of content, social networking, the sharing of taste and relevance, connectivity, and collective intelligence. Auvinen (2019) has also defined Social media as a new information network and information technology that uses a form of communication utilizing interactive and user-produced content, and where interpersonal relationships are created and maintained. Social Networking Sites (SNS) like Facebook and YouTube are used for this purpose.

Facebook is one of the most widely used (SNS). It was launched in 2004, primarily for Harvard University students, and was opened to the public in 2006. Since its inception, the site has achieved immense recognition, and its popularity is increasing day-by-day (Phang and Ming, 2021). On the other hand, YouTube is becoming a major resource for sharing

and consuming video content. It is gaining immense popularity and support from viewer community due to its comprehensive repository of videos. Also, it supports diversity by having different facets such as modals, languages, domains and cultures. Therefore, the advancement of Facebook and YouTube are considered to be a factor that if well utilized will at least address the challenging situation and attitudinal problems encountered by the students of Office Technology and Management in the Polytechnic.

Attitude is a part of human psychology against unacceptable behaviours. It centres on the social behaviour, perception, reaction, and disposition of an individual to others around him (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2020). There is a positive and negative attitude. A positive attitude is an acceptable attitude due to favourable behaviours and dispositions. A negative attitude is the opposite of a positive attitude due to unfavourable behaviours and dispositions. Both of them affect youths because the majority of users are them.

Statement of the Problem

There is no doubt that social media enhances the societal development and personal growth of students because they can get useful information from the internet. Many lectures and teachings have been held through social media. However, social media has its downside in which when students are not well monitored it will affect them negatively. Many Office Technology and Management (OTM) students have been victims of time mismanagement, bad reading habits, lateness, truancy, and absenteeism from lectures due to excessive use of Social Media. On the other hand, some students find it easy to learn theoretical and practical skills in OTM thus there are so many negative influences and positive influences on OTM students learning, but these influences are many and not known as there is limited literature about Social Media and the student's attitude to OTM.

This was proved by Adegboyega (2019). Incidentally, OTM lecturers are quite busy preparing their lectures, assignment, test, practical and exams not knowing that there is one concealed factor that influenced the attitude of their students which is Social Media. Lecturers do not have enough time to sit, discuss and counsel their students on the negative aspect of Social Media in learning OTM as the factors are not outlined. From the foregoing it is an indication that if students do not have sufficient communication skills together with practical skills their chances for meeting employability skills standard in the knowledge-based economy thereby affecting OTM students' attitudes towards utilization of social media platforms as part of the basic content of the curriculum.

Purpose of the Study

The main aim of the study is to find out the influence of Social Media on Office Technology and Management (OTM) Students' Attitude toward learning in Federal Polytechnics in North-east Nigeria. Specifically, the study was sought to:

1. Determine the influence of the use of Facebook on OTM Students' attitude toward learning in Federal Polytechnics in North-east Nigeria.
2. Determine the influence of the use of YouTube on OTM Students' attitude toward learning in Federal Polytechnics in North-east Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following question were raised:

1. What is the influence of the use of Facebook on OTM Students' attitude toward learning in Federal Polytechnics in North-east Nigeria?
2. What is the influence of the use of YouTube on OTM Students' attitude toward learning in Federal Polytechnics in North-east Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are formulated:

H₀₁: Use of Facebook has no significance influence on OTM students' attitude toward learning in Federal Polytechnics.

H₀₂: Use of YouTube has no significance influence on OTM students' attitude toward learning in Federal Polytechnics.

Literature Review

Concept of Social Media

Social media becomes one of the main sources for people to obtain information. This media is divided into two types, namely print and non-print media. Print media obtain information through printed mail, newspapers, magazines, and dailies. Whereas, non-print media obtain information from radio, television, and social media like Twitter. Media remains a tool, which renders helps people across the globe to influence their opinion, attitude, and knowledge. According to Lateef (2021), Social Media utilization furnishes individuals with information in any sector of life. Through media, there has been a lot of development and growth that occurred due to the availability of platforms that allows them to get linked to the entire universe and contribute to global development. As Social Media utilization increases, many people including youths use it to find out about the historical development of society, concepts, religion, etc.

Social media is a form of effort for people, especially students, to get or move close to each other on the internet or social contacts by making connections through individuals. Social media is the social interaction among people who create, share, and exchange information and ideas in environments, schools, workplaces, homes, communities, etc. Social media, regardless of distance, facilitates people to communicate, and convey information in the form of images, videos, and audio. Social media has been used increasingly in many cultures so the number of users also has increased geometrically over the years. Today, people use SM daily for its numerous advantages and side effects (Lateef, 2021)).

A Brief Historical Overview of the Social Media

Many people like to link the history of social media to the growth in communication technology that has been occurring since the end of the 19th century. A common starting point is Samuel Morse's first telegraph, which he sent in 1844 between Washington, D. C and Baltimore (Bruns, 2021). However, this type of communication does not qualify as social media. First, it did not take place online. Second, telegrams do not contribute to any larger community. Instead, they are used to send individual messages between two people. So, while it is interesting to think of social media as being part of a much larger continuum, the real history of social media starts in the 1970s with the emergence of the internet. The first two social media sites were Six degrees and Friendster, both of which are no longer around, despite playing an influential role in starting what has become a social media revolution.

According to Owusu and Agatha (2021), Six degrees is considered to be the first social media site because it allowed people to make individual profiles and add others to their network. It was officially launched in 1997 and lasted until 2001. A year later, in 2002, the site Friendster emerged. Like Six degrees, it allowed users to make contacts and save them as part

of a personal network. People could also share videos, photos, and messages with other users and they were also able to leave comments on other people's profiles, so long as they were part of each other's network. Social media later expanded. Sites like Myspace and LinkedIn gained prominence in the early 2000s and sites like Photobucket, and Flickr facilitated online photo sharing, YouTube came out in 2005, creating an entirely new way for people to communicate and share across great distances (Bruns, 2021). Bruns (2021) wrote that by 2016, Facebook and Twitter both became available to users throughout the world. These sites remain some of the most popular social networks on the internet (Owusu & Agartha, 2021).. Other sites like Tumblr, Spotify, Foursquare, and Pinterest began popping up to fill specific social networking niches. Today, there is a tremendous variety of social networking sites, and many of them can be linked to allow cross-posting. This creates an environment where users can reach the maximum number of people without sacrificing the intimacy of person-to-person communication. We can only speculate about what the future of social media may look like shortly but it will exist in some form or another for as long as humans are alive.

Facebook

Facebook, among other social media and social networking sites, has grown exponentially over time to become the biggest and most popular social networking site with an online population of above 1 billion active users, as of the end of 2012 (Manca, 2020), and still counting. Its introduction has become one of the most important social trends of the past decade. Available in over 70 languages, Facebook has sure become a global phenomenon and experience. Facebook was founded in 2004 by college students at Harvard, namely Mark Zuckerberg, Eduardo Saverin, Dustin Moskovitz, and Chris Hughes. Its initial reach started in February 2004, for Harvard students only, and by 2006, it has become a regular platform in all American Universities. The aim was to offer each registered user the chance to create a user profile with pictures and to keep in touch with their so-called "friends", or contacts they link to on the site. It was however opened for public use in 2006. Between 2006 and 2008, it had become a popular sought-after social media globally. Being a Facebook user is not just limited to sharing information with a group of friends. Through groups, users can form new networks and communities. A user's posting, in the form of text, pictures, video, or a combination, can receive feedback from other users known as "friends" in the form of the "Like" button or "comment" option. They can also forward the posting to their own Facebook contacts using the "Share" option. That is how information can get viral on Facebook. Having such huge online citizens as registered users, Facebook undoubtedly has become a nation of its own (Fletcher, 2019).

Facebook has dominated the social networking world with its growing popularity and rapid growth in terms of its users. Since its inception it has been growing around developed as well as developing countries. It was started as a small application for university students to connect and interact with each other and now it has turned in to the largest and most popular social networking site in the world. Social networking media has given the internet a new participatory direction by creating the space for user-generated content. Its multifunctional use increases the interpersonal connectivity and hence helps in relationship maintenance (Fletcher, 2019). Social networking sites such as Facebook provide an inexpensive and easy medium to develop and maintain such interpersonal relationships (Rajeev & Jobilal 2019).

YouTube

YouTube is the Internet's leading video service. Owned by Google, it began operating in 2005, and grew very rapidly, with 50 million visits to the site just by the end of the same year. By 2010, there were already more than 2 billion visits to YouTube every day. Today, it has become the leading video-sharing site in the world (Auvinen, 2019). Jenkins (2020)

argues that YouTube is a site for the reproduction and distribution of grassroots media and that participation on YouTube occurs on the level of production, selection, and distribution. Visitors to YouTube are offered the opportunity of accessing videos, produced by both amateurs and professionals, on varieties of topics and on just about anything in the world (Auvinen, 2019).

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of the study was all the 981 HND and ND OTM students from the four (4) Federal Polytechnics located in Northeast offering OTM as a course of study. The sample size for this study was two hundred and sixty-nine (269) students as recommended by Cohen Table of sampling. While proportionate stratified random sampling technique was used to select sample from each of the Polytechnics involved in the study. A questionnaire titled “Influence of Social Networking Sites on Students’ Attitude Toward Learning (ISNSSATL)” was used as the instrument for data collection which consists of three constructs, Influence of the use of Facebook, YouTube and Students Attitude with it four points rating scales. The instrument was validated by three experts.

The instrument for data collection was pilot-tested on 22 Office Technology and Management students from Federal Polytechnic, Daura, Katsina State located in the North-west Nigeria which is not part of the population of this study. The researcher recorded a response returned rate of 100% and was analyzed using Cronbach Alpha to determine the internal consistency of the instruments. The reliability coefficient of 0.99 was found. The instrument was administered and retrieved by the researcher with the aid of research assistants. Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23 was used throughout the process. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer all the research questions while simple linear regression was used to test the null hypotheses. For decision, the benchmark of four points rating scale is 2.50 (Okolocha & Nwadiani, 2019). Following their recommendation, any item on the questionnaire with a mean value of 2.50 and above will be considered agreed while any item with a mean value of less than 2.50 will be considered disagreed. Additionally, any hypothesis with a P-Value of less than 0.05 will be rejected while any hypothesis with a P-Value above 0.05 will be accepted.

Results

Research Question one: What is the influence of the use of Facebook on OTM Students’ attitude towards learning in Federal Polytechnics in North-east Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on Influence of the use of Facebook on OTM Students’ attitude towards learning in Federal Polytechnics in North-east Nigeria

S/N	Items	N	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Use of Facebook influences your attitude towards producing mailable documents of different forms using Microsoft Office Word	258	3.05	.734	Agreed
2	Use of Facebook influences your attitude towards applying suitable format to various kind of document	258	3.10	.685	Agreed
3	Use of Facebook influences your attitude towards creating and organizing database system	258	3.14	.770	Agreed
4	Use of Facebook influences your attitude towards designing and maintaining a webpage	258	2.91	.779	Agreed
5	Use of Facebook influences your attitude towards producing data using spreadsheet	258	2.93	.766	Agreed
6	Use of Facebook influences your attitude towards demonstrating basic knowledge of networking system in the office	258	2.95	.752	Agreed

7	Use of Facebook influences your attitude towards using internet technology to source for current information	258	3.00	.811	Agreed
8	Use of Facebook influences your attitude towards sharing ideas with colleagues using video conferencing	258	3.05	.772	Agreed
9	Use of Facebook influences your attitude towards using search engine to locate valuable information	258	2.98	.815	Agreed
10	Use of Facebook influences your attitude towards retrieving information from electronic files	258	2.92	.790	Agreed
11	Use of Facebook influences your attitude towards demonstrating basic knowledge of desktop publishing	258	2.93	.773	Agreed
12	Use of Facebook influences your attitude towards sending information within and outside the organization using email	258	3.07	.753	Agreed
13	Use of Facebook influences your attitude towards maintaining information security in the office	258	3.02	.813	Agreed
14	Use of Facebook influences your attitude towards updating various software and antivirus programme when the need arises	258	2.96	.788	Agreed
15	Use of Facebook influences your attitude towards demonstrating basic knowledge of Microsoft power point for presentation	258	2.88	.816	Agreed
Grand Mean			2.99	.774	Agreed

Source: Field work (2023)

The result of descriptive statistics documented in table 1 indicated that the mean and standard deviation scores of all the items ranging between 2.91 and 3.14 with a standard deviation of .734 and .816 with a grand mean of 2.99 respectively. The results agreed that Facebook has a positive influence on OTM students' attitude towards learning in Federal Polytechnic in North-east Nigeria.

Research question two: What is the influence of the use of YouTube on OTM Students' attitude towards learning in Federal Polytechnics in North-east Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on Influence of YouTube on OTM Students' attitude towards learning in Federal Polytechnics in North-east Nigeria

S/N	Items	N	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Use of YouTube influences your attitude towards producing mailable documents of different forms using Microsoft Office Word	258	2.83	.830	Agreed
2	Use of YouTube influences your attitude towards applying suitable format to various kind of document	258	2.95	.762	Agreed
3	Use of YouTube influences your attitude towards creating and organizing database system	258	2.91	.768	Agreed
4	Use of YouTube influences your attitude towards designing and maintaining a webpage	258	2.82	.833	Agreed
5	Use of YouTube influences your attitude towards producing data using spreadsheet	258	2.81	.833	Agreed
6	Use of YouTube influences your attitude towards demonstrating basic knowledge of networking system in the office	258	2.91	.735	Agreed
7	Use of YouTube influences your attitude towards using internet technology to source for current information	258	2.86	.775	Agreed
8	Use of YouTube influences your attitude towards sharing ideas with colleagues using video conferencing	258	2.94	.767	Agreed
9	Use of YouTube influences your attitude towards using search engine to locate valuable information	258	3.00	.761	Agreed
10	Use of YouTube influences your attitude towards retrieving information from electronic files	258	3.04	.662	Agreed

11	Use of YouTube influences your attitude towards demonstrating basic knowledge of desktop publishing	258	3.16	.832	Agreed
12	Use of YouTube influences your attitude towards sending information within and outside the organization using email	258	3.20	.752	Agreed
13	Use of YouTube influences your attitude towards maintaining information security in the office	258	3.18	.785	Agreed
14	Use of YouTube influences your attitude towards updating various software and antivirus programme when the need arises	258	3.07	.750	Agreed
15	Use of YouTube influences your attitude towards demonstrating basic knowledge of Microsoft power point for presentation	258	3.08	.807	Agreed
Grand Mean			2.98	.777	Agreed

Source: Field work (2023)

The result of descriptive statistics documented in table 2 indicated that the mean and standard deviation scores of all the items ranging between 2.81 and 3.20 with a standard deviation of .662 and .833 with a grand mean of 2.98 respectively. The results showed that YouTube has a positive influence on OTM students’ attitude toward learning in Federal Polytechnic in North-east Nigeria.

Null Hypotheses One: Use of Facebook has no significance influence on OTM students’ attitude towards learning in Federal Polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria.

Summary of results of testing Null Hypothesis 1 is presented on Table 3

Table 3: Linear Regression of respondent on the Use of Facebook Influence on OTM students’ attitude toward learning in Federal Polytechnics in North-east Nigeria.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.977 ^a	.954	.954	.11465

a. Predictors: (Constant), Facebook

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	69.701	1	69.701	5302.268	.000 ^b
	Residual	3.365	256	.013		
	Total	73.066	257			

a. Dependent Variable: Attitude

b. Predictors: (Constant), Facebook

The result on Table 3 reveals $R^2=0.954$, $F(1,256)=5302.268$, $p=0.000$. Since the -value is less than the alpha level of the test ($p<.05$), the null hypothesis tested is rejected. This means that Use of Facebook has significance influence on OTM students’ attitude toward learning in Federal Polytechnics in north-east Nigeria. This result does not support the prediction of hypothesis one that says Use of Facebook has no significance influence on OTM students’ attitude toward learning in Federal Polytechnics in north-east Nigeria.

Null Hypotheses Two: Use of YouTube has no significance influence on OTM students’ attitude towards learning in Federal Polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria.

Summary of results of testing Null Hypothesis 2 is presented on Table 4

Table 4: Linear Regression of respondent on the Use of YouTube Influence on OTM students’ attitude toward learning in Federal Polytechnics in North-east Nigeria.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.809 ^a	.654	.653	.31412

a. Predictors: (Constant), YouTube

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	47.806	1	47.806	484.485	.000 ^b
	Residual	25.260	256	.099		
	Total	73.066	257			

a. Dependent Variable: Attitude

b. Predictors: (Constant), YouTube

The result on Table 3 reveals $R^2=0.654$, $F(1,256)=484.485$, $p=0.000$. Since the -value is less than the alpha level of the test ($p<.05$), the null hypothesis tested is rejected. This means that Use of YouTube has significance influence on OTM students’ attitude towards learning in Federal Polytechnics in north-east Nigeria. This result does not support the prediction of hypothesis two that says Use of YouTube has no significance influence on OTM students’ attitude towards learning in Federal Polytechnics in north-east Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of research question one which is supported by test of its corresponding null hypothesis revealed that use of Facebook has a positive influence on OTM students’ attitude toward learning in Federal Polytechnics in North-east Nigeria. The finding is consistent with Osharive, (2018) study which focused on Social Media and the Academic Performance of Students at the University of Lagos. The study revealed that academic performance of a great number of students at the University of Lagos is influenced by social media. In a related study, Ikezam and Maxwell (2021) Investigated the Influence Of Social Media On the Academic Performance Of Senior Secondary School Students In Rivers State: Implications For Counselling. The findings revealed that the use of Facebook, WhatsApp, and YouTube can influence the academic performance of students in Rivers State. Similar finding was reported by Manca (2020) who wrote on Approaching the Use of Facebook to Improve Academic Writing and to Acquire Social Competences in English in Higher Education in University of South Africa (UNISA), South Africa.

The findings of research question two and the test of its null hypothesis indicated that use of YouTube has a positive influence on OTM students’ attitude toward learning in Federal Polytechnics in North-east Nigeria. The findings concurred with the arguments in the existing literature, such as the study conducted by Moneeba, Sohail and Zahid (2019) on the Impact of YouTube Tutorials in Skill Development among University Students of Lahore. Moneeba et al. proved that YouTube has a significant impact on youth regarding tutorials. YouTube being a part of advanced web 2.0 technology is gaining its roots strong in education purposes especially in the individual or intrapersonal aspect. In another study by Abubakar and Musa, (2020) on the Impact of Social Media on Academic Performance among Undergraduate Students of Bayero University, Kano. The paper reveal that Educators and students can use social media as informational and communicational tools to ease and improve the learning process.

Conclusion

The current study empirically investigated the influence of social media on OTM students' attitude toward learning. The study proved that effective utilization of social media platforms such as Facebook and YouTube will positively influence students' attitude toward learning. Therefore, if students will have sufficient communication skills together with practical skills their chances for meeting employability skills standard in the knowledge-based economy will be high, thereby affecting OTM students' attitudes towards utilization of social media platforms as part of the basic content of the curriculum.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Government through School Management and Lecturers should give more emphasis on the importance of communication skills together with practical skills in the use of Facebook to students in order to meet up with the employability skills standard in the knowledge-based economy.
2. Government through School Management and Lecturers should give more emphasis on the importance of communication skills together with practical skills in the use of YouTube to students in order to meet up with the employability skills standard in the knowledge-based economy.

References

- Abubakar U.S., Musa A.A. & Nasir U. (2020). Students' Attitude Towards the Use of Social Media for Learning Purposes. *Journal of Literature, Languages and Linguistics*, 9(9),102-116.
- Adegboyega M. I. (2019). Impact of Students' Attitudes towards Social Media Use in Education on their Academic Performance. *Journal of Management & Research*, 10(2/4), 21-34.
- Adaja P. O., & Ayodele F. (2021). Promoting Positive attitude Through the Enhancement of youtube utilization for Students in Oyo State Tertiary Institutions for Sustainable Development. *Nigerian Journal of Business Education* 7(1), 43-56.
- Auvinen, S. M. (2019). Excelência profissional: a convergência necessária de variáveis psico lógicas. *Estudos de Psicologia* (Campinas), 32(4), 763-771. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/0103-166X2015000400019>
- Baird S. & Fisher T. (2020). The emergence of social media: development, trends, and challenges. *Entrepreneursh.Theory Pract.* 29, 577–597.
- Baykul S. H. (2019). Bridging the Valley of Death: Lessons Learned From 14 Years of Commercialization of Technology Education. *Academy of Management Learning & Education*, 8(3), 370-388
- Bruns B. I. (2021). Peaks, slumps, and bumps': individual differences in the development of creativity in children and adolescents," *New Directions for Child and Adolescent Development*, 4(6), 123-142.
- Fletcher V. (2019). Social Networking Research Revisited: The Case of Higher Education. *Academy of Management Learning & Education*, 4(1), 22-43.
- Ikezam D.G. & Maxwell F. (2021). Cultural and Outcomes-Related Issues in Implementing an Interdisciplinary Cross-Campus Entrepreneurship Education Program. *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship*, 23(special issue), 733-746.
- Jenkins, R. (2020) "Globalization, corporate social responsibility and poverty", *International Affairs*. 81,(3), 525-540.
- Kaplan, A. & Haenlein, U. (2020). A school is "a building that has four walls with tomorrow inside": toward the reinvention of the business school. *Bus. Horiz.* 61, 599–608. doi: 10.1016/j.bushor.2018.03.010

- Lateef, A. O. (2021). Modern Office Technology and the Performance of the Professional Secretary in Contemporary Organizations in Ghana. *Information and Knowledge Management*, 3(4)52-57.
- Macnamara, U. & Zervas, S. E. (2018). The Nature of Philosophy of Social Media and the Nigerian Polytechnic Education. *International Journal of Innovative Social Sciences & Humanities Research*, 6(3) 25-32
- Manca, S. (2020). Snapping, pinning, liking or texting: Investigating social media in higher education beyond Facebook. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 44, 100707.
- Okolocha, C. C., & Nwadiani, C. O. (2018). Assessment of Utilization of ICT Resources in Teaching among Tertiary Institution Business Educators in South Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 4(1), 1-10.
- Osharive T. (2018). Examining the formation of social media in entrepreneurship: a meta-analysis of entrepreneurship education outcomes. *J. Bus. Ventur.* 28, 211–224. doi: 10.1016/j.jbusvent.2012.03.002
- Owusu G. & Agartha F. (2021). Concepts into practice: meeting the challenge of development of social media around an innovative paradigm: The case of the International Entrepreneurship Educators' Programme (IEEP). *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research*, 17(2), 146-165.
- Phang I. & Ming C. (2021). Information Analyst intentions among University Students in Italy *J of Glob Entrepres* 8, 20 <https://doi-org/10.1186/540497-0107-5>, 11(3), 46-63.
- Rajeev E. A. & Jobilal, F. (2019). Students' Involvement in Social Networking and Attitudes towards Its Integration into Teaching. *International Education Studies*, 9(9)250-260.
- Tabachnick, B. G., & Fidell, L. S. (2018). *Using multivariate statistics*. Boston, MA: Pearson.
- Verdegem F. (2019). Does Assessment Kill Student Creativity? Educational Forum, the. Kappa Delta Pi. 3707 Woodview Trace, Indianapolis, IN 46268–1158, 9(4), 111-127.